

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spin Trapping Studies of Paramagnetic Transients appearing in the Photo-oxidation of Organic Compounds with Metal Ions

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The long-standing problems of the mechanism of photo-oxidation of organic molecules with metal ions has been explored in some details by electron paramagnetic resonance spin trapping studies coupled with matrix isolation method. The present review gives an account of these studies which provide an insight in the variety of mechanisms of these important organic reactions.

Electron paramagnetic spectroscopy (epr) is now firmly established as a technique for studying both the structures of organic radicals and other paramagnetic transients and the mechanisms of reactions in which they take part. The potential of epr spectroscopy for the study of radical-mediated processes in solution was exploited only slowly because of the transience of most radicals and difficulty in producing them in sufficient detectable concentrations. Various methods have been developed to overcome this problem including high-energy in situ radiolysis¹, high-intensity photolysis² and rapid-flow techniques³. However, these methods found little favour as these were found expensive and cumbersome for their general and regular use. The use of radical addition reactions to detect paramagnetic transients was first proposed by Janzen⁴. Since then this technique for which Janzen and Blackburn coined the name 'spin trapping' has been extensively developed with applications appearing in the various fields⁵. Now this method coupled with matrix isolation method (trapping of paramagnetic transient in solid/rigid matrix at low temperatures) has become the method of choice for studying free radical reactions in solution.

The present communication gives a brief overview of the epr spin trapping studies coupled with matrix isolation method used in elaborating and supporting various mechanistic pathways by the detection and characterisation of paramagnetic-transients appearing in the photo-oxidation of organic compounds by different metal ions.

Role of metal ion oxidants in organic oxidations

In terms of their role in elementary kinetic step, metal ion oxidants function either as one or two equivalent reagents. Reactions involving multiequivalent oxidation in a single stage are considered unlikely. Indeed, even single-stage, two equivalent processes seem comparatively rare. In the thermal and or photo-oxidation reactions of organic substrates with metal ions, the most frequently encountered mechanisms correspond to an electron transfer between substrate and metal ion accompanied by the breaking of either C-H or C-C bond and loss of a proton to leave a substrate radical which is then subsequently removed from the system by a number of ways, such as either by further oxidation or by disproportionation or by coupling with another radical or by reaction with oxygen to give peroxy radical. Variations on this mechanism can be observed in certain cases and the mechanism complexities can be understood by knowing the nature of transient species.

Photo-oxidation by metal ions

Lead(IV)tetra-acetate⁶ was the earliest oxidant which was used to generate several radicals by the well known photo-oxidative decarboxylation of different carboxylic acids (eqn. 1),

2-methyl-2-nitrosobutan-3-one and t-nitrosobutane were used as spin traps and it was tentatively concluded that acetoxy radicals were spin trapped

prior to rapid decarboxylation reactions. Thus these two views made the inferences somewhat suspect.

Several organometallic compounds of lead, tin and mercury were photolysed in presence of α -phenyl-t-butyl nitron (PBN) and several alkyl radicals were spin trapped. However, these studies⁴ were directed mainly towards the generation and identification of different types of radicals to judge the potential and versatility of spin trapping agents.

Cerium(IV)⁷ salts solutions in various organic media were photolysed at 77 K and the solvent-derived radicals were detected and identified from their characteristic epr spectra. In these photo-oxidation reaction, C-C bond fission processes were found to be prominent with tertiary alcohols and carboxylic acids, whereas with simple (primary) alcohols, amides and other compounds, the abstraction of hydrogen atom from an activated C-H bond was found. Carbon-centred (hydroxyalkyl) and oxygen-centred (alkoxy) radicals were spin trapped by 2,3,5,6-tetramethylnitrosobenzol (nitrosodureol, ND) during the photo-oxidation of alcohols by cerium(IV)⁸ suggesting the hydrogen abstraction and electron transfer mechanisms in these reactions. The spin trap nitrosodurene (ND) was found to be quite stable in presence of several metal ion oxidants in neutral solutions. But surprisingly, in these experiments of photo-oxidation of alcohols by cerium(IV)⁸, epr signals due to nitrosodurene anion radical (ND⁻) were observed and it was shown that ND⁻ stemmed from secondary photoreaction of NO₂⁻ (from ceric ammonium nitrate salt).

Uranium(vi) photochemistry has been extensively investigated⁹ and it is still an active field of research. In aqueous solution the quenching processes of luminescence from excited uranyl ion (UO₂²⁺) by a variety of substrates were studied and several mechanism were proposed on the basis of free radical trapped by spin trapping agents and in solid matrix¹⁰.

Mechanistic considerations of uranium(vi) photo-oxidation were centred around two main ideas, namely, the 'kinetic encounter' (eqns. 2-4) and 'complex formation' theories¹⁰ (eqns. 6-7).

The uranium(V) was considered to disproportionate as

The prior existence of U^{VI}-substrate complex supported by independent optical measurements which thereafter undergoes charge-transfer to metal (CTTM) breakdown to give free radical (eqns. 6, 7) was the main consideration of the complex formation theory¹⁰,

Kinetic encounter mechanism was proposed for the photo-oxidation reactions of many substrate molecules on the basis of trapping of several substrate derived radicals in organic matrices at 77 K. Abstraction of hydrogen atom from a carbon atom adjacent to an activating group, such as CO, CN, COOH, CHO, OH, CONH₂, COOR and C-C bond cleavage with secondary and tertiary alcohols, ketones, some carboxylic acids and diethyl ether, was proposed to explain the trapped radicals. In the liquid phase spin trapping study¹¹, it was shown that (UO₂²⁺)^{*}, which so far was known to react with alcohols exclusively by α -hydrogen abstraction reaction (eqn. 8) can also react by electron transfer reaction (eqn. 9),

The alkoxy radicals (RCH₂O[•]) were trapped for the first time and it was indicated that the concentration of spin trapping agent is crucial for trapping a particular type of radical^{11,12} (Fig. 1).

The concentration of uranyl salt was also found to be an important factor in trapping of different types of radicals. It was observed that at high concentration of UO₂²⁺ (>1 mol dm⁻³), methyl radical was trapped in the rigid matrix at 77 K during the photo-oxidation of ethanol. With the decrease in concentration of UO₂²⁺, CH₃C[•]OH

radical became important. These results suggest that charge transfer mechanism (eqn. 10) is also important which is followed by C-C bond cleavage

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of spin adducts of PBN with (a) $\text{Me}_2\text{CHO}^\bullet$ (b) $\text{Me}_2\text{CHO}^\bullet$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{C}^\bullet\text{OH}$ (c) $\text{Me}_2\text{C}^\bullet\text{OH}$ when PBN had (a) higher, (b) intermediate, (c) lower concentrations during the photo-oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by UO_2^{2+} .

(eqn. 11) to explain the formation of $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_3$ radical in the ethanol rigid matrix¹³. The trapping of $\text{CH}_3\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}$ radical at lower concentrations was attributed to either direct abstraction of hydrogen atom from ethanol molecule by excited uranyl ion (eqn. 8) or by the hydrogen abstraction by ethoxyl or methyl radicals from the surrounding ethanol molecules (eqn. 12)

Other interesting results of these studies¹⁰⁻¹³ include the trapping of benzyl radical from the photolysis of uranyl perchlorate in benzyl alcohol¹⁰ (eqn. 13), trapping of NO_3^\bullet from the direct photolysis of uranyl nitrate and the production of alcohol radicals by secondary route¹² (eqn. 14),

A water-soluble spin trapping agent, sodium-2-sulphanatophenyl-t-butyl nitron (SPBN)¹⁴ was used in the photolysis of uranyl nitrate in aqueous solutions of diols, triols and hexitols¹⁵. Hydrogen atom abstraction mechanism was considered to explain the trapped carbon centred free radicals ($\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}(\text{CHOH})_n\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) formed in these photoredox reactions¹⁵.

Iron(III) perchlorate and chloride salts were found to be an effective photo-oxidant for a wide range of organic compounds from the results obtained by both spin trapping¹⁶ and matrix isolation methods¹⁷. The results of spin trapping studies¹⁶ substantiated both hydrogen abstraction (eqn. 8) and electron transfer (eqn. 9) mechanisms in the photo-oxidation of various alcohols. Its general behaviour was found to be similar¹⁷ with that of cerium(IV)⁷ and uranium(VI)¹⁰ as it was observed that C-C bond fission processes were prominent with tertiary alcohols and carboxylic acids, whereas with primary alcohols, amides and certain other types of substrates the abstraction of hydrogen atom from an activated C-H bond was found¹⁷. Alkyl radicals were trapped at 77 K during the photo-oxidation of tertiary alcohols by both ferric chloride and perchlorate. This was explained in terms of C-C cleavage photoprocess earlier found with cerium(IV)⁷ and not with the uranyl salts¹⁰ (eqns. 15 and 16),

Towards carboxylic acids Fe^{III} showed ambivalent behaviour. Alkyl radicals were always trapped at 77 K in most of the reactions which indicated the preference for photo-decarboxylation over the expected hydrogen atom abstraction process which was observed only with isobutyric acid when the seven line epr spectrum was observed due to $(\text{CH}_3)_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{COOH}$ ¹⁷.

Chromium(vi) is another important photo-oxidant which was used in a detail spin trapping study of photo-oxidation of alcohols¹⁸. The photolysis of crown ether (18-crown-6) complexes

Fig. 2. Epr signals due to two different chromium(v) intermediate formed during the photo-oxidation of alcohols by chromium(vi).

of potassium chromate in several alcohols produced different types of free radicals, such as alkyl, alkoxy and hydroxy alkyl. Two different relatively long-lived chromium(v) intermediates were also observed (*g* values : 1.968 and 1.979) (Fig. 2). The hydrogen abstraction (eqn. 8) and electron transfer (eqn. 9) mechanisms were proposed to account for the trapping of carbon-centred and oxygen-centred radicals by α -phenyl-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (PBN) and nitrosodurene (ND). These spin trapping agents also trapped the fragmented radicals of crown ether (eqn. 17).

Vanadium(v)¹⁹, molybdenum(v)²⁰ and cobalt(III)²¹ complexes and other complexes of different metal ions were photolysed in various organic media particularly alcoholic media in presence of spin trapping agents²². In addition to the expected substrate derived free radicals, several other paramagnetic inorganic species, like $H\cdot$, $Cl\cdot$, $N_3\cdot$, $\dot{C}N$, $\dot{O}H$, O_2^- and also like solvated electrons and metal-centred free radicals were spin trapped²².

VOQ_2OCH_3 solution in benzene was photolysed in presence of α -phenyl-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (PBN) and epr spectra corresponding to spin adducts of PBN with $CH_3\dot{O}$ and $\dot{C}H_2OH$ were obtained¹⁹. It was shown that the trapping of a particular radical depended on the concentration of spin trap. The results were explained by assuming that $CH_3\dot{O}$ was the primary radical which isomerised into $\dot{C}H_2OH$ (eqns. 18 and 19),

Photoreaction of octacyanomolybdate(v) in methanol/methylene chloride yielded many adducts of α -phenyl-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (PBN) and nitrosodurene (ND)²⁰. The formation of various organic and inorganic paramagnetic species by outer- and inner-sphere mechanisms was explained by the following scheme :

Alkoxy radicals were spin trapped during the aerobic photolysis of alkyl cobalt(III) complexes²¹. However, it is not clear that whether these radicals were really produced by the cleavage of cobalt peroxy complex or were the products of the decay of peroxy spin adducts.

In another study, the organic free radicals were spin trapped from the photoreaction of cobalt(III)-copper(II) ion-pair with tetra-phenyl borate²³. However, these studies¹⁹⁻²³ were directed more toward the photochemistry of the coordination compounds rather than the mechanistic pathways of the photo-redox reactions of organic compounds with metal ions.

Tungsten(vi)²⁴ and titanium(IV)²⁵ oxides dispersed in various organic media including alcohols, were photoirradiated and different substrate derived free radicals, such as alkoxy, hydroxyalkyl,

hydroxyl, hydrocarboxylic, hydrogen and solvated electrons were spin trapped by using α -(1-oxo-4-pyridyl)-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (POBN), 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-*N*-oxide (DMPO) and 2-methyl-2-nitrosopropane (MNP) spin trapping agents. The photoreactions were explained by the following scheme :

(hole) (solvated electron)

However, it was not clear that which of the possible pathways (eqn. 24 or 25) were dominant in the production of $\text{CH}_3\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}$, although the results of this study²⁴ showed that water played an important role in these reactions and therefore the formation of $\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}$ was the first step in these photo-processes. These results are not directed only towards the mechanistic studies but these have been used in various important photochemical reactions such as water splitting²⁶, photo-catalysis²⁷ and photo-degradation of pollutants²⁸.

Platinum(IV), palladium(IV) and iridium(IV) hexachloro salts have been used in the photo-oxidation reaction of several organic compounds. The recent surge of interest in the long established problem²⁹ of photoactivation of hexachlorometalate(IV) (where metal is Pt, Pd or Ir) ions reflected many viewpoints³⁰⁻³². The activation of alkanes by (PtCl_6^{2-}) by ion under photo-irradiation represented the important singular advance and the same group characterised the photo-reduction of (PtCl_6^{2-}) by CO and acetone³⁰. The 488 nm photo-reduction of (PtCl_6^{2-}) by alcohols³³ led to the production of colloidal platinum(0) in mild and controlled way with obvious potential in formulation of photocatalysis.

Photo-irradiation of (PtCl_6^{2-}) solution in acetone³⁰ produced a σ -acetyl complex of platinum(IV). Prolonged irradiation yielded $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2$ and paramagnetic platinum(III)

species³⁴, detected by epr spectrum at 77 K. This carbon-centred radical of acetone was also spin trapped in the photo-oxidation reaction of hexachloropalladate(IV) and -iridate(IV) with various aldehydes and ketones including acetone³⁵. The proposed mechanism of the photo-oxidation of acetone by PtCl_6^{2-} involved an electron transfer from the enol tautomer of acetone to PtCl_6^{2-} ³⁰(eqns. 26-28),

The results of a detailed spin trapping studies of photo-oxidation of various alcohols by these oxidants³² indicated that on mild photolysis both carbon- and oxygen-centred radicals derived from alcohols were produced. Prolonged wide band photolysis lead to the production of hydrogen due to the formation of colloidal metal at the later stage of photolysis (Fig. 3). All these radicals were spin trapped by α -phenyl-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (PBN) and sodium-2-sulphanatophenyl-*t*-butylnitron (SPBN) in neat and aqueous alcoholic media.

The production of alkoxy radical was attributed to direct attack of $((\text{MCl}_6^{2-})^*)$ upon the O-H group of alcohols (eqn. 29). An alternative pathway involving Cl^\cdot as precursor of $\text{RCH}_2\text{O}^\cdot$ was also indicated (eqns. 30 and 31),

The RCHOH was assumed to be originated either by the direct attack of $(MCl_6)^{2-}$ * upon the C-H bond of RCH₂OH, or via secondary hydrogen

Fig. 3. Epr spectrum (a) of a radical mixture CH₂OH and H obtained on prolonged irradiation of hexachloroplatinate(IV) ion in methanol-water mixture in presence of spin trap SPBN. Computer simulated (b) spectrum based on coupling constants given for spin adducts of $\dot{C}H_2OH$ (1) and \dot{H} (2) with SPBN.

transfer reaction of RCH₂O \cdot (eqn. 32) or by the isomerisation reaction (eqn. 19) or by reaction involving Cl \cdot as precursor like the one shown in eqn. 31.

In this study³² also Cl \cdot had been spin trapped from the photolysis of (AsPh₄)₂MCl₆ in CH₃CN and CH₂Cl₂. The epr spectrum of the spin adduct of α -phenyl-*N*-*t*-butylnitron (PBN) with Cl \cdot had the splitting parameters comparable with the one reported in the earlier study³⁶.

The cryogenic photolysis of these salts in several organic media yielded two sets of species at 77 K, namely, the matrix derived organic radicals and the paramagnetic Pt^{III} and Pd^{III} centres (Fig. 4). These results supported the mechanistic considerations of these photo-redox reactions.

Fig. 4. Epr spectrum (first derivative) obtained on photolysis of hexachloropalladate(IV) ion in CH₃CN at 77 K indicating the signals due to paramagnetic species Pd^{III} and $\dot{C}H_2OH$ at *g* values 2.184 and 2.0036 respectively.

Hexachloropalladate(IV) and -iridate(IV) were used in the photo-oxidation of aldehydes and ketones³⁵, and hexachloroiridate(IV) was used in photo-oxidation of monosaccharides including alditols³⁷. The results of these studies^{35,37} revealed the spin trapping of C-centred radicals derived from these substrates by the hydrogen atom abstraction mechanism (eqn. 8).

The photochemical transformation of PtCl₆²⁻ complexes in different organic media including particularly methanol is still being detailed out³⁸ by epr and flash photolysis studies. The results of these studies centred round two main views about the primary photoprocess: the one considered that the reaction proceeded via the intermediate complex of trivalent platinum whereas the other view is that the primary process is the electron transfer from the solvent molecule (methanol) to the excited (PtCl₆²⁻)* and then the platinum(III) complex is formed by the dissociation of platinum(IV) complex. New radical complexes like (PtCl₆³⁻-R) and (PtCl₆³⁻-RO₂) were shown to exist and the formation of radical cation has been shown to

explain the trapping and observation of different radicals at 77 K (eqns. 33–36),

Thus, it is obvious that this photo-reaction and others still need elaborations of their mechanisms and particularly that of their initial photo-processes and the spin trapping studies³² extended in these direction can lead to some important clues.

Conclusions

Epr spin trapping studies supported by matrix isolation method have provided valuable information about the paramagnetic transients appeared in the photo-oxidation of organic compounds by metal ions. This in turn has elaborated and supported the mechanistic pathways and helped in studies of some unknown photo-reactions. These studies also have a potential to be developed into industrial procedures like the generation of well characterised metal colloids³⁴ and other photochemical reactions of current interest like water splitting²⁶, photo-catalysis²⁷ and photo-degradation of pollutants²⁸.

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